

EDUCATION - SOCIAL AND EDUCATIONAL COMMUNITY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article gives information about analyses of upbringing's social-spiritual criteria in the New Uzbekistan creations.*

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Today, provision of quality education open to the youth and in accordance with the requirements of the times is one of the leading issues of our social policy. In particular, the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said: "It is known that education of the young generation has always been important and relevant [1]. However, in the 21 st century in which we live, this issue is really becoming a matter of life and death. Therefore, it is appropriate to emphasize the need to "educate young people who think independently, who are able to take responsibility for the future of our country, who are enterprising and enthusiastic" [2]. In this sense, as defined in the concept, in particular, it implies the formation of moral, civil, intercultural, spiritual, social qualities of virtue in students, as well as the development of a democratic society. This, in turn, demonstrates the integration of education and training with the processes of rapid reforms in the conditions of today's modernizing Uzbekistan.

Continuous spiritual education is considered a huge social process, and personnel training has a special place in it. When young parents asked the great encyclopedist Ibn Sina to bring up their child, Ibn Sina asked when the child was born, and it is said that they were late in raising the child, which means that the conclusion is that raising a child is an extremely sensitive matter. It is necessary to perform the services of educating the young generation, bringing them to adulthood in a healthy and mature manner, in cooperation with parents and flawlessly. In a word, it requires constant study and continuous research. Because it is clear to everyone that the noble goals can be achieved only through high spirituality and continuous education. At this point, an important question arises, what caused the need for continuous and systematic teaching of Education in grades 1-11 of general secondary schools?

To prepare students for a successful social life in a rapidly changing world, qualities such as responsibility, commitment, legal awareness and legal culture, deep worldview, healthy faith, enlightenment, religious and national tolerance, spiritual, civil, intercultural sociality are used. Formation is becoming the main issues on the agenda. There are also problems in the education of young people, such as the inability to correctly assess the complex geopolitical and ideological processes taking place in the world, the inability to make correct decisions in solving social problems, and the inability to formulate specific goals related to finding one's place in life. These, in turn, create the basis for wide-scale spread of evils such as disconnection of family-society relations, indifference, crime, easy acceptance of various manifestations of "popular culture".

It is the education and training system in the country that is an important factor in the implementation of national ideals and ideological ideas. After all, the young generation learns the

national principles rich in socio-spiritual, educational experience collected in educational institutions on a scientific and educational basis in the educational system. In fact, it is impossible to convey spirituality to a person without education and make a decision. Carrying out education and upbringing in harmony leads to economic, social and spiritual growth. [3].

If we analyze from the learned experiences, if pedagogues approach each child in the group based on respect, if they carry out their activities based on careful study of psychological aspects of children, it will serve to increase the love of any child towards education. Children feel comfortable and relaxed when they see and feel that others accept and respect each of them, while actively pursuing their personal interests [4].

It should be noted that Conception embodies the pedagogical experience and achievements of the world. Including the educational recommendations of the European Union, individual freedom, entrepreneurship, the pursuit of success in the US experience, inculcating customs and moral ideals in the minds of young people in South Korea, Japan's "education for character formation", China's goodness, righteousness, purity, wisdom and reliability Pedagogical experiences aimed at training such qualities were studied. As we know from history, we can see that education is a very sensitive issue and was constantly under the attention of foreign statesmen. Mustafa Kemal, the great statesman of Turkey, was asked about education: Who would you be if you were not the president of the republic? Mustafa Kamal said without thinking: I would become the Minister of Education! Atatürk had such thoughts. He wanted to raise a generation that would be in line with his wishes. Minister of Education... He looks like a chef. He will either poison your food and kill you. Or, by preparing sweet food, it will cause your health and well-being. Minister of Education...He looks like an engineer. He destroys the young generation. Or wake him up and wake up the nation at the same time. Therefore, the government and the statutes put people selected on the basis of certain criteria into this "post". We can cite the countries of Japan, Singapore, Germany and Finland as an example of the secret of the Minister of Education and his role in the fate of the nation. In the concept, great importance is attached to the work carried out on the scientific and technological reform of youth education in Uzbekistan on a modern basis and to the work of forming it based on scientifically based basic competencies and qualities based on the needs of today. For this purpose, the socio-pedagogical cooperation of family, pre-school education, general high school, special vocational high school, higher education institutions, neighborhoods will rise to a new level. At this point, the earlier education starts, the more effective it will be, taking into account that it is important to start and effectively organize moral education in preschool education organizations, which are the first link of the continuous education system [5].

Therefore, the upbringing of children in the family is expressed by continuity and systematicity, based on the transfer of traditions such as family duty, respect, loyalty, honor, which exist in the family and everyday life from generation to generation [6]. The importance of the preschool period is invaluable for the development of the child's personality as a whole. All important features, inclinations and abilities of a person are formed in preschool age.

Also, a person brought up in a healthy family should always strive to build a fair society and develop it, to live in peace and harmony. The concept envisages a new, systematic approach to education, the full use of the pedagogical capabilities of the family, preschool and general secondary education institutions in the guaranteed design and teaching of basic qualities, and raising scientific-methodical cooperation between them to a new level. In this Concept, special

attention is paid to legal pedagogical opportunities in the education of young people [7]. In the words of our head of state, unprecedented attention is being paid to the fundamental reform of the national education system based on the idea that "New Uzbekistan begins at the school threshold". A lot of work is being done to develop the fields of science, culture and art, literature, and sports, to increase the efficiency of spiritual and educational work, and to realize the talents and abilities of young people, especially our girls".

A personality-social approach to the problems of legal education and upbringing is assumed. This means that the pedagogue treats the student as a subject of educational interaction aimed at discovering and developing the individuality of each person's unique and phenomenal. Dealing with boys and girls as subjects of life, helping and supporting them in finding their own spheres and ways of being, serves to acquire the capacity for "adaptive phenomenology". The education, worldview and upbringing of young people have a special place in the development of our country and the prosperous life of our people.

After all, the success of the reforms and the worthy place of our country among the developed countries in the world is primarily related to the development of education. The reason for this is that today, along with the wide range of opportunities, the space of information has also expanded, various ideas, views, technologies for their promotion, and factors influencing social consciousness and thinking have increased. How we raise our children, what personal qualities we develop in them, taking into account their individual and gender characteristics, directly depends on what kind of woman and man they will be in the future, what kind of parents they will be for their children. Therefore, protecting the minds and thinking of our youth and children from foreign and harmful influences, filling the gaps by directing their inner world towards perfection is one of the urgent issues of today.

During the past 30 years of independence, life itself requires putting a person's life, dreams, pains and concerns on the agenda and increasing the efficiency of the scope of work in this regard. But time itself shows that the problems that need to be solved are also related to the daily concerns of families, which are the main link of society.

The importance of continuous spiritual education is that educational education in kindergartens, schools, lyceums, colleges, technical schools and higher education institutions is combined with spiritual education in the family. This is the most important task within the scope of the Development Strategy implemented in Uzbekistan. Now, in all higher military educational institutions, in the process of training and education of professional officers, it theoretically serves as a program for them to work in the spirit of patriotism.

When we study scientific research on the Uzbek model, rule of law, legal culture, justice, enlightenment, economic and social spheres, we witness that national sources on this topic are directly related to independence. Many dissertations, monographs, pamphlets, and research works on this issue are studied and analyzed by the authors. Effective organization of these works today is becoming a demand of the times. Therefore, through continuous spiritual education, not only in pre-school and post-secondary education, but also in non-specialist areas of military and higher education institutions, when teaching the topic of the rule of law, the conceptual foundations of legal culture, the subject-related philosophy, law, political science, it is possible to summarize the approaches within the fields of sociology, cultural studies, psychology and pedagogy and emphasize that a certain scientific result can be achieved.

On the basis of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 No. PQ-2909 "On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System" based on the fundamental improvement of the higher education system, based on the priority tasks of the socio-economic development of the country, personnel it can be seen that the issues of fundamentally revising the content of training, ensuring the creation of the necessary conditions for the training of highly educated specialists at the level of international standards are a strategy focused on practicality and effectiveness. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" № PF-5847, setting priorities for the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan The goal of raising the process of training of highly qualified personnel with high spiritual and moral qualities to a new level in terms of quality, modernization of higher education, development of social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies is certainly important for national progress. Is one of the steps.

At the core of all our activities, the main goal is to improve the way of life, life and spiritual world of this people, to put the factors of stability, consistency and quality at the main level in the activities of every field. People living in society must first have a clear goal and a path leading to it. A person should be in constant motion, search, discover new opportunities, create good living conditions not only for himself, but also for those around him, and contribute to the development of society and the state. It is aimed at further increasing the effectiveness of the ongoing reforms, creating favorable conditions for the all-round rapid development of the state and society, raising the development of our country to a higher level, and ensuring stable competition with the world community. This is why an actionable Action Strategy is key to our massive fundamental progress spanning the next hundred years. It is the right of our multi-ethnic people to live in peace that is at the root of all actions that ensure legality and justice in the mutual relations between man and government, society and the state. Also, the launch of "Generosity and Support" charity work during the quarantine period is one of the most important aspects of the principle of humanity.

Therefore, every citizen living in our country should live with the spirit of faith in the society.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. Physically and spiritually mature young people are our support and support in achieving our noble goals / "Khalk sozi", July 1, 2017.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" №. PF-4947 // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, №. 6, Article 70. Zamonov Z. O'zbekiston ijtimoiy-siyosiy hayotida ma'naviy-axloqiy institutlarning o'rni. Siyos.fan.dok. (PhD) ilmiy daraja olish uchun.diss. –T.: 2019. – 68 b.
3. Zamonov Z. The role of spiritual and moral institutions in the socio-political life of Uzbekistan. Doctor of political science. (PhD) for the degree.diss. - T.: 2019. - 68 p.
4. Tojiboyeva H.M. Issues of development of cooperation between preschool educational institution and family // Ensuring integrity and continuity of education - an important criterion of the development of the field: materials of the Republican scientific-practical conference (book 6). - T.: TDIU, 2015. - p. 81-83.

5. Consultation for parents "Gender education of girls and boys in the family". https://gym1534uz.mskobr.ru/dou_edu/gbou_detskij_sad_1204/obrazovanie/methodical_cabinet/konsul_taciya_dlya_roditelej_gendernoe_vospitanie_devocheki_malchikov_v_seme.
6. Kholmatova Z.T. Pedagogical essence and characteristics of the concept of "gender" in the context of education. "Integrative-innovative approaches in primary education at the level of the Republic of Uzbekistan". Materials of the republican scientific and practical conference held on May 6, 2019. -271 p.
7. Consultation for parents "Gender education of girls and boys in the family". https://gym1534uz.mskobr.ru/dou_edu/gbou_detskij_sad_1204/obrazovanie/methodical_cabinet/konsul_taciya_dlya_roditelej_gendernoe_vospitanie_devocheki_malchikov_v_seme.